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Creation and collapse of the Eastern Bloc – Russian-Ukrainian war – The Hungarian Revolution of 1956 – Testimonies about life in the Eastern Bloc in the 1970s

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Abstract

This article is divided into three parts:

The Eastern Bloc and the USSR, its collapse and the Russian-Ukrainian war -

The Hungarian revolution of 1956, the communist regime and the liberation of the USSR's satellite countries from 1989 onwards - A collection of testimonies on daily life under the socialist-communist regime in the 1970s. In the aftermath of World War II, the Soviet Union was led by Joseph Stalin, who seized control of certain Eastern European and Central European countries to form the Eastern Bloc. In 1989, the Soviet Union's satellite countries decided to leave the Eastern Bloc. In 1991, the USSR collapsed. From 1989 onwards, the satellite countries underwent a often brutal transition from communist rule to a market economy, which was not always well managed. Capitalism was a dream for many people in Eastern and Central Europe, but disillusionment seems to have gradually extinguished their hopes for a better life, if we are to believe their testimonies. This new vision has created a certain nostalgia for the past.

In the aftermath of 1989, many people were considered unproductive: this was the case for Roma and low-skilled people, who were seen as unfit for work. Following the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989 and the collapse of the USSR in 1991, NATO welcomed most of Russia's former satellite countries, which was then greatly weakened. The future became uncertain and the world became dangerous, on the brink of a Third World war. This research also provides a brief overview of the 1956 Hungarian Revolution to understand what happened. The aim of this research is to collect the words of 12 people about their perceptions of everyday life in the 1970s. This period is considered to have been the heyday of a certain level of prosperity in Hungary and East Germany, under the yoke of the socialist-communist regime in the Eastern Bloc. What were the conditions of daily life in these countries? The testimonies provided a better understanding of their daily lives at that time. They expressed their feelings about their experiences during that period in relation to their current lives.

I. Brief overview of the creation of the Soviet bloc, its decline, and the collapse of the USSR. The causes of the Russian-Ukrainian war and the confrontation between the West and Russia. The emergence of the desire for a multipolar world.

The Eastern Bloc began to take shape in 1944. It consisted of communist regimes in countries under the control of the Soviet Union. In 1948, the Eastern Bloc consisted of the following countries:

East Germany, Poland, Czechoslovakia (consisting of the Czech Republic and Slovakia, which formed a single state), Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, and Albania.

The present-day Ukraine was part of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), along with the Baltic states: Estonia, Lithuania, and Latvia.

Yugoslavia, led by Tito, was a collection of small regions integrated into the country known as "Yugoslavia." Although Yugoslavia was a communist regime and had close ties to the USSR and the Eastern Bloc, it managed to preserve a form of autonomy and independence from the USSR while maintaining privileged relations. In 1989, the satellite countries of the USSR that made up the Eastern Bloc collapsed, with one major event in particular: the fall of the Berlin Wall separating East from West. Hungary was praised by West Germany for its active and positive attitude during the fall of the Berlin Wall.

Before 1989, a political (communist), economic, and military alliance (the Warsaw Pact) strengthened ties between the satellite countries and the USSR. 1991 is the official date of the implosion (or collapse) of the USSR. The following 15 states became independent following the collapse of the USSR:

Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan.

Russia is considered the successor state to the USSR. In 1990, among the 15 states, the three Baltic countries demanded their independence. The remaining 12 countries also seceded, going on to form the CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States). Vladimir Putin, acting in tandem with Medvedev, initially took power on an alternating basis, before handing over the presidency to Vladimir Putin.

The ruling power discreetly transformed a moribund Russia into a more competitive and better organized country, not to mention remilitarizing it. The army was reorganized, with purges within the "Nomenklatura .

Meanwhile, the Balkan War in the 1990s led to the break-up of Yugoslavia through the intervention of NATO, which did not have a UN mandate. Neither Russia nor Serbia accepted this intervention, which they considered illegal. Russia, still weak, was unable to exert pressure or intervene in the Balkan War. The West, feeling all-powerful as the world's sole superpower, supported the Maidan coup in Kiev, Ukraine. This coup (which removed a legitimately elected president from office) led to the ouster of President Viktor Yanukovich in February 2014, who was forced to flee the country to Russia.

After the breakup of Yugoslavia and the probable loss of Ukraine, Russia felt threatened by the West.

Why? Because this new situation could create a direct border between NATO countries and Russia. This situation had become unbearable for Russia. Volodymyr Zelensky took power, promising to resolve the issues peacefully with Russia. Western countries had an interest in opening their doors to Ukraine, rich in black soil and rare minerals.

Why? Because the European Union (EU) is a colossus with feet of clay, as it is sorely lacking in raw materials and rare earths. The vast country of Ukraine, larger than France, could provide an alternative to dependence on Russian gas and oil. This is undoubtedly why Western countries, with the help of the US, intervened by arming Ukraine and reinforcing fortress cities such as Toretsk and Pokrovk.

Suspensions of Western intervention, including by the US, were raised by Moscow, which denounced the presence of instructors and mercenaries in Ukraine. The West's constant denials have become less and less credible with the increase in deaths in Ukraine of people from Western countries.

Little by little, the Russian-Ukrainian war has turned the world upside down: mistrust of the global South towards the Western bloc, which is seen as hypocritical and using a policy of "double standards". The global South, Russia, China, India, and some South American countries have criticized the West for its "double standards" policy. Westerners are accused of being "preachers" hypocritical "neocolonialists" who grant themselves freedom of action without UN approval or arrogate to themselves the right to wage war wherever they want without a UN mandate. This was the case in the wars in Yugoslavia, Iraq (under G.W. Bush) and elsewhere. By playing the role of world policeman, has the West not flouted international law?

Another counterproductive action by the West was the decision to freeze Russian assets, which undermined confidence in the West. Indeed, this move created mistrust among third countries, which asked themselves the following question: "What if tomorrow we are next on the West's list?" Let us remember that the military intervention in Iraq, without a UN mandate, followed by drastic sanctions, led to a catastrophic situation, causing hundreds of thousands of deaths among the population due to a lack of water and medicine.

Russia was very isolated at the outset because of Western sanctions, but it recovered somewhat and managed to reorient itself commercially, much to the surprise of the West. The more the West tightened the screws, the more Russia thwarted the sanctions and found allies in China, India, and other countries.

The confrontations between the West and Russia have generated a desire in Africa to break free from alliances that are seen as a form of neo-colonialist control over African countries. As a result, France has lost trade alliances in Africa to China and Russia, which are seen as “equal” partners.

The concentration of Western weapons in Ukraine to defeat Russia left Russia with no choice but to forge alliances with countries such as Iran and North Korea, which are arms suppliers. China also helped Russia in its hour of need in 2023, and India did the same by massively increasing its purchases of Russian oil. After India refined Russian oil, European countries bought Russian oil at a higher price, but under the Indian banner! The hypocrisy is total in the sense that Westerners were well aware of the origin of the refined oil.

The Russians' “special operation” in Ukraine has, over time, become a real proxy war in which the first victims were the Ukrainians. In the end, Russia had to live in a war economy and rearm itself more and more to face the onslaught of highly sophisticated Western weapons. Defend Ukraine or weaken Russia?

I think the intention was to do both. Unfortunately for Western forces, Russia proved to be united and highly resilient, and by mid-2024, Russia had gradually shifted from a defensive to an offensive position, with Ukraine's weakness becoming increasingly apparent since February 2025.

The West's position has at times been quite surreal: while some 40 countries were able to supply weapons to Ukraine, Russia was singled out for having asked for help from a handful of countries such as North Korea, Iran and China. The latter has never acknowledged its assistance to Russia.

Currently, the situation is becoming more dramatic for Ukraine: the EU no longer has any reserves to help Ukraine and believes it will have to borrow \$2 trillion to recover and continue to support Ukraine at the same time. Some EU member states do not wish to participate in a joint loan of this magnitude. Germany, Europe's largest economy, has weakened economically, France is virtually bankrupt, its president is heavily criticized, social unrest is beginning to emerge, countries such as Slovakia and Hungary are exercising their veto rights, the right-wing AFD party is gaining ground in Germany, the conservative right is becoming a force to be reckoned with in Austria, and in Spain there are riots against migration policy, etc.

Has the EU become ill, due to miscalculations in its geopolitical and economic choices? Has it mismanaged its migration policy? Is it becoming a behemoth on the verge of becoming a superstate subjugating sovereign countries? Is the EU becoming increasingly centralized, with the risk of becoming a future “USSR”? Or, on the contrary, is the EU becoming increasingly fragile?

It is clear that since Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the cutting off of Russian gas and oil supplies, and the explosion of the Nord Stream gas pipelines under the Baltic Sea, the EU has found itself in an unprecedented energy crisis. The 18 packages of sanctions, which appear largely ineffective, have had a boomerang effect, as the cost of living for EU citizens has risen sharply. Poverty has increased, the number of “socially excluded” people is growing, and around one in seven children do not have enough to eat or live in a family in precarious circumstances.

The EU has gone from dependence on Russian gas to dependence on US shale gas, which is three times more expensive, drastically reducing European competitiveness. Uncle Sam can no doubt be rubbing his hands with glee: arms sales and shale gas have already brought him hundreds of billions of dollars. The EU has reached the dramatic point where it must try, as best it can, to find alternative sources of energy elsewhere.

- Unfortunately, the EU has destroyed its diplomatic and trade relations with Russia to such an extent that it will be difficult to reestablish relations once a lasting peace agreement has been reached. To get out of a position of weakness and regain a dominant position, the current US president has recently imposed tariffs ranging from 10% to 35% on products from third countries and the EU. Will the world fight back? Only time will tell. But it is clear that US hegemony, still the world's leading economic and military power, is losing ground in the face of a world that no longer wants to obey the existing world order. The consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war have had a global impact:
- Many countries want to break away from the dollar
- The BRICS countries are growing stronger, opening the door to a multipolar ideology in the face of the Western “monopolar” and “globalist” trend.
- Russia is no longer isolated, while Western countries are no longer followed in their ideology, values, and desire for globalization
- Sovereignty movements are gaining strength and momentum in Europe and elsewhere
- Faced with a world population of 8 billion, the West, with around 1 billion inhabitants, is no longer able to impose its laws and its vision of the world as it would like

In Ukraine, pogroms against the Russian-speaking population, the ban on Russian speakers speaking their mother tongue, the conflict in Donbass, large-scale corruption in the country, and increasingly brutal and contested forced conscription are certainly not signs of democracy. The same is true for other minorities in Ukraine: the Magyars, Gypsies, and Romanians. Yet the EU remains silent and continues to support Ukraine in the war, hoping to integrate Ukraine into the EU, thereby opening up the possibility of a huge market and

immense resources. Does the end justify the questionable means? The future will tell, because as the saying goes, "You can't make an omelette without breaking eggs ! "

Many are trying to hide the reality: the war was undoubtedly provoked and encouraged by the West and began as early as 2014. It was following the annexation of Crimea without a single shot being fired and the official recognition of the Donbass regions (Luhansk and Donetsk) by Russia that the war with the West really began. The mainstream media dates the start of the war on February 24, 2022, when the Russian president ordered the start of special operations (so according to Russia, there is no war).

There were indeed neo-Nazis in the Azov troops glorifying their Nazi idol Bandera, but the question is whether or not this should be generalized. However, it is true that in some cities in the country, especially in western Ukraine, one can find statues of Bandera covered in flowers. Were not many Ukrainian soldiers found when Mariupol was taken by the Russians? Need we remind you that during World War II, the regime in power in Ukraine committed atrocities and murders against Jews? Added to this is the ongoing corruption: did the current president not admit to the US president that more than \$100 billion cannot be accounted for in terms of its destination or final use?

Ukraine joining the EU under the current conditions seems more like a thorn in the EU's side than an advantage. Prime Minister Viktor Orban recently stated that Ukraine's integration into NATO would mean immediate war with Russia, a major nuclear power (with around 5,200 bombs at its disposal).

Need we also recall the 2014-2015 "Minsk Agreements," which proposed peace? The words of Angela Merkel and François Hollande exposed the manoeuvres to stop Russia's progress in Ukraine, which was running out of steam.

In "Le monde en devenir" (The world in the making), a strategic column published on Friday, January 6, 2023, we read the following:

« Following the admissions on December 7 by Angela Merkel and former President François Hollande, who was alongside the German chancellor during the negotiations for the 2014-2015 Minsk agreements, it seems clear that the agreements were not intended to guarantee peace, but to allow the Kiev regime to 'buy time' and rearm ».

For President Vladimir Putin, this deception on the part of the West was unacceptable; moreover, the aim was to weaken Russia by using Ukraine, hence the idea of a proxy armed conflict. The West would therefore have provoked a fratricidal war to weaken Russia.

The Minsk Protocol signed on December 5, 2014, was an agreement aimed at ending the war in Donbass. A ceasefire protocol concerning the Donbass region (Minsk II) was signed on February 11, 2015, given the failure of the 2014 Minsk agreement. Under the auspices of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), the participants in the Minsk II summit brought together the leaders of the following countries: Russia, Ukraine, France, Germany, and the Donetsk and Luhansk regions.

The aim was to agree on measures concerning the war in Donbass.

The breakdown of the Minsk Protocol was formalized by Russia's official recognition of the independence of the Donetsk and Luhansk People's Republics on February 21, 2022.

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After the breakup of the USSR, Russia considered it intolerable that the Atlantic Alliance (NATO) reaching Russia's borders. With the Minsk agreements being flouted, according to Moscow, the Russian-Ukrainian war increasingly became a proxy war, with the main suppliers of arms to Ukraine being the US under President Biden and the Western world.

The Western world probably thought it could bring Russia to its knees, perhaps even break it up. By supplying weapons to the Ukrainian army and imposing more than 17,000 economic sanctions, the aim was undoubtedly to paralyse bank transfers by removing Russia from the SWIFT banking system. In addition, the West froze more than \$300 billion in Russian assets to undermine Russia's objectives.

Despite all its efforts, the West was unable to achieve its goals. The reality on the ground and the global upheaval overwhelmed the West, which was trying to go all in, having invested so many billions in this war. Unfortunately, misjudgments and poor strategic choices have meant that it is the populations of Western countries who are still paying the price today, through reduced purchasing power. The precariousness is increasing with the rise in the price of basic consumer goods. The sanctions against Russia also seem to be having a "boomerang effect," hitting people in their wallets.

Why so much effort to continue the war? Breaking Russia by sending weapons in abundance during the Biden administration, with Europe's increasingly significant involvement, is undoubtedly one answer to that question. Europe is not a land of minerals or sufficient agricultural land: Ukraine offered an ideal solution. It was the solution that created the possibility of economic expansion coupled with greater autonomy for the EU. But cutting itself off from Russia to obey Uncle Sam has effectively made the EU a vassal state.

The tide has turned with Donald Trump back as President of the United States. During the campaign, the EU was openly hostile to him, with the exception of Hungary. President Trump has undoubtedly not forgotten this, nor has he forgotten the hypocritical behaviour. Indeed, Joe Biden ultimately withdrew in favour of Kamala Harris, who is supported by the EU.

It was therefore predictable that President Trump would disengage from the Russian-Ukrainian war, which concerns his predecessor and the EU more than it does him. After hundreds of billions of dollars in arms were given by the West to Ukraine, arms shipments began to decline, with the EU being asked to take over.

The prospect of losing Ukraine would be a bitter defeat for the EU, difficult to explain to Europeans who are increasingly tightening their belts because of the costs of war aid. If this failure were to be confirmed, the fate of Europe would be bleak. Let us hope that the blind rush forward of certain leaders does not lead us into a Third World war.

For the US, things are not so simple either. What are the dangers for the US?

- The rapprochement between Russia and China is very worrying.
- Africa is welcoming Russia and China with open arms.
- The economic development of the BRICS countries
- Economic alliances with Russia
- The threat to the dollar in commercial transactions
- China's threat to retake Taiwan
- India's refusal to obey the West, opting instead to continue trading with Russia
- Internal unrest and opposition beginning to emerge in the US and Europe
- The threat of a new world order beyond the control of the US
- The threat of a crushing defeat against Russia, which has swallowed up hundreds of billions. Failure would be very difficult to justify. The same goes for the EU.

Did the predecessor of the current US president misjudge the forces involved? Was he too optimistic about the outcome of this proxy war against Russia? Could peace not have been achieved in Istanbul if the Ukrainian president had not listened to those who wanted the war to continue?

Will this story end with the final question: "All these deaths for nothing?"

Is there not a risk that responsibility will be diluted, with a few scapegoats being found to act as a smokescreen? Are the people of the EU not at risk of paying a heavy price for a war they did not choose? Why is Hungary the only country that has had the courage to opt for popular consultations? Ultimately, has the Europe of our fathers, who sought common prosperity in peace, been betrayed by the EU's current choices? The resolute globalist European union has the duty to ask its citizens about their future, isn't it?

The Russian-Ukrainian war seems to have created other easily observable factors:

- Mistrust of Western countries among African and Asian countries.
- Certain South American countries, such as Brazil, which is a giant in terms of population and economy, have taken a pro-Russian stance.
- Russia's alliance with China, Iran, and North Korea is becoming increasingly apparent.
- African countries (the Global South) and the Third World want economic independence.
- The gradual disengagement of certain Third World countries from Western countries.
- India, which has not forgotten its colonial past with Great Britain, continues to trade with Russia despite Western sanctions.
- The gradual rapprochement between Russia and China, which is greatly feared by the West in geopolitical and economic terms.
- Opposing visions between South Africa and Western countries.
- The emergence of a multipolar world view that escapes the West.
- The development of the BRICS, expanded to include other important countries such as Egypt and Saudi Arabia is becoming a major economic competitor for the G7.
- The decline in the use of the dollar in transactions is beginning to weaken the US, but also in the West.
- The emergence of "sovereignists" opposed to the "globalist" project of Western countries.
- The "double standard" policy, often used by the West and considered hypocritical and unfair, is increasingly being revealed in the news.
- South Africa denounces the "double standard" policy.

- The EU risks entering an unprecedented recession due to an energy shortage that could bring the economic engine to a halt.
- Russia appears less isolated than Western countries, which seem unable to find a way out of the situation for which they are largely responsible.
- Asian, Middle Eastern, and North African countries have not forgotten the organized coups and questionable interventions, sometimes without a mandate. The West does not seem to be getting good press for these events.
- China and Russia are investing heavily in Africa, which is welcoming them.
- The catastrophic demographics of Western countries do not seem to be offset by migration, which, if poorly managed, is creating more and more social unrest.
- The freezing of Russian assets is an unprecedented move, undermining the rest of the world's confidence in the West.

Western countries, once colonizers and “world police” until now, are becoming a weakened bloc, with an undeniable human factor: low population growth rates. The West is becoming a large minority: 1 billion inhabitants compared to 7 billion, out of a global population of 8.062 billion in 2023. It is undoubtedly possible that the world order could be overturned by alliances in Asian countries, drawing in other countries from the rest of the world. Contrary to all expectations, it is not Russia that is isolated, but increasingly the Western bloc.

Have we gone too far? Is this a point of no return? Only time will tell. As Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán keeps saying, “the diplomatic route is the only option that can get us out of this mess, not war.” A redefinition of healthy political and trade relations is the only way to build trust. Good relations require a “win-win” trade perspective. This implies truly sovereign states, thus ruling out “globalism.”

Given that fertility rates in Africa are very high compared to Western countries, where they are dangerously low, this could lead to significant migration problems if migration is poorly managed in terms of reception and without a real integration policy. Poorly managed migration can lead to destabilization and an even greater risk of marginalization in Western countries.

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II. Brief summary of events surrounding the Hungarian Revolution of 1956

At the end of World War II, in 1944-45, the Russians had joined forces with the Americans and their allies in Berlin. This situation led to the division of Germany into two parts, with the erection of a wall in Berlin the erection of a wall between Western and Russian forces. Russia and the United States, the great victors of the war against Hitler's Nazi Germany, divided Europe in two; with the Russians taking the Eastern European countries and certain Central European countries: East Germany, Poland, Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, and Albania, which became “satellite countries” of the USSR. The three Baltic countries, Lithuania, Estonia, and Latvia, were integrated into the USSR. The Warsaw Pact was created (May 14, 1955), uniting the satellite countries politically, economically, and militarily with the USSR. This pact was a symmetrical response to NATO. The Warsaw Pact was dissolved on July 1, 1991, shortly before the dissolution of the USSR in 1991.

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Matyàs Ràkosi, alias Máttyàs Rosenfeld (1892-1971) took power in Hungary from 1948 to 1956. He was the first President of the Council of Ministers, then became Prime Minister of the Republic of Hungary in 1953-1953. He was responsible for purges, imprisonment, and political liquidations. Anti-Semitism flourished under and after Ràkosi's regime, even though he himself was of Jewish origin. Following his arrival in power,

Khrushchev forced him to resign and go into exile in the USSR. Rákosi made the mistake of following the Stalinist line and the cult of personality, which had been banned by Khrushchev. He joined Joseph Stalin's anti-Semitic campaign in 1953. Rákosi's expression "salami technique" referred to the elimination from power of everything that was not communist: the Church, political parties, dissidents, and opponents of the regime. His successor was Imre Nagy, born in 1896 and summarily executed in 1958 along with another architect of the 1956 Hungarian Revolution, Péter Maléter, who was also executed. Péter Maléter, who was also executed.

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The Hungarian uprising was a popular revolt largely initiated by students against the Hungarian communist regime and its policies imposed by the USSR. The Stalinist regime had become intolerable for the population due to constant repression. Added to this were the major economic difficulties Hungary was experiencing in 1956.

Censorship and the secret police, known as the AVH (államvédelmi hatóság), acted brutally, imprisoning, torturing, and killing opponents of the regime. One of the most notorious prisons at the time was in Recsk, which was referred to as a "labour camp" (1950-1953), but in reality was a "Hungarian Gulag." Other sordid places still existed in 1956 where torture and execution were practiced. The spark that ignited the powder keg came when the secret police (AVH) began firing on the crowd in Budapest.

In 1956, the economic crisis was severe, and it is important to note that a significant portion of agricultural and industrial production was sent from satellite countries to the USSR.

During the 1956 Revolution, Prime Minister Imre Nagy decided to withdraw from the Warsaw Pact. This was the last straw for Nikita Khrushchev, who ordered the revolt to be crushed, and Soviet troops (around 200,000 soldiers) invaded the country and entered Budapest on November 4, 1956.

Kádár János (1912-1989) arrived on November 7, 1956, with a convoy of Soviet tanks. He was installed by the USSR to lead the country. He announced the formation of the "Revolutionary Workers' and Peasants' Government (Magyar Forradalmi Munkás-Paraszt Kormány). He led the People's Republic of Hungary until 1988.

Alongside repression, torture of opponents, and purges, Kádár attempted to liberalize the country somewhat. For example, he eased religious repression and allowed a certain amount of political dissent under strict control, giving the country a somewhat democratic image. He even decriminalized homosexuality in 1961. Unlike his predecessor Rákosi, he rejected anti-Semitic policies. Under his regime, it is true that Hungary offered better living conditions than most other countries in the Eastern Bloc.

Thus, Russian troops arrived in Budapest with tanks. According to renowned historian Mária Schmidt (Hu), the invasion was carried out by Soviet troops, but also with Ukrainian soldiers. She replied to John Cleese as follows: "The invasion was carried out by Soviet troops, including Ukrainians..."

But why did the West not respond to Hungary's request for help in 1956?

Péter Szijjártó, Minister of Foreign Affairs of the current Hungarian government, recently stated the following: "... In 1956, during the Hungarian Revolution, the Hungarians asked the West for help, but in vain... "

Finally, how many victims were there in the Revolution? Approximately 2,500 killed

Approximately 13,000 wounded. More than 200,000 people fled the communist regime. The two main routes out of the country were Austria and Tito's Yugoslavia.

Mass emigration took place between November 1956 and March 1957.

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III. The importance of collecting testimonies from people who lived through the 1970s

Much has been written about the Hungarian uprising and revolution of 1956, but there have not been many collections of testimonies from people who lived through the period between 1945 and 1989. I wanted to fill this gap by going out into the field to ask people about their experiences during this period, and more specifically during what is considered to be the most prosperous period: the 1970s. What were the conditions of daily life? What do they think of their current situation?

I believe it is important to preserve their memories, given that the target population was between 25 and 30 years old in 1975, meaning they were born between 1945 and 1950. These are people who can recount their experiences firsthand. In 2024, they will be between 74 and 79 years old.

3.1. Methodological approach

This research project is focused on qualitative analysis, with analysis of the target population's statements.

3.2. Target population, ages, and countries of origin

Twelve people born between 1945 and 1950.

Six people (three men and three women) from Hungary, including:

Two in Budapest, two in Szászvár, and two in Komló

Two people (one man and one woman) from Slovakia (Kosice)

2 people (1 man and 1 woman) for Romania (Satumare)

2 people (1 man and 1 woman) for Serbia (Subotica)

3.3. Composition of the target population

The target individuals who agreed to be interviewed are currently aged between 74 and 79.

3.4. Conditions for approaching the target population

All individuals had Hungarian as their mother tongue and lived either in Hungary or in a region with a significant Hungarian minority (> 10%).

3.5. Selection of interviewees

Gender parity was respected in order to obtain a wider range of information.

Anonymity had to be respected at the request of the participants. Only the initials of the individuals are mentioned, along with their gender and age.

IV. Questions asked

Can you describe daily life in the 1970s and the importance of the family? Do you feel nostalgic for the old regime? Is it better now? What form of censorship did you notice during that period? Can you tell me about the school system? Regarding the culture? About religious freedom? Were people suspicious of each other? Can you talk about the school system, the culture, religious freedom? What do you think of your current situation?

Note: during the conversation, forgotten questions were revisited.

V. Answers to the questions asked (translation)

A. Can you describe daily life in the 1970s and the importance of the family?

B. Are you nostalgic for the old regime?

C. Is it better now?

D. What forms of censorship did you notice during that period?

E. Can you tell me about the school system?

F. About the culture?

G. Religious freedom?

H. Were people suspicious of each other?

I. Can you talk about the school system, culture, religious freedom?

J. What do you think of your current situation?

1. Hungary, Budapest, Witness 1, female, 74 years old

Under the Kádár regime, it was better, I have to say. When I hear what my parents said about Rákosi, it was terrible with him. People were arrested for the slightest thing, imprisoned, tortured. In the 1970s, we had enough to eat and a certain standard of living. People went to restaurants several times a week, and there was gypsy music in many restaurants. Heating, electricity, and water were very cheap. School was free, as was healthcare. But you still had to give something under the table to get good service. In the countryside, I remember my aunt bringing fruit and eggs. Others brought meat or money. We had a work book that was often checked. Not going to work was severely punished by the police. Everyone was afraid of the police. The hardest thing was leaving the country to go to Austria to see a cousin who had fled in 1956. People knew each other and knew who they could talk to openly without getting into trouble with the police or the authorities. That said, nothing was completely safe, because there could always be a “brick” around the corner. Bricks were spies, informers.

Culturally, it was a pretty rich period, because folklore was quite lively, unlike today, and music was everywhere. But now there’s a renewed interest in all that. Ultimately, what I’m nostalgic for about that period is the closeness of people, the mutual support, and families that were less fragmented than they are today. What’s better now is that there’s more freedom to say what you think... sometimes even too much. Cities and the countryside were much cleaner. Nowadays, people are more isolated. There are ways to get rich, but not for many. I don’t really know how to choose between the past and the present.

2. Budapest, Witness 2, male, 75

I have mixed feelings, actually. For example, I had to wait almost five years to get my Trabant, and there was very little choice. Yes, there was the two-stroke Wartburg, but it didn’t run well. The Skoda was better, but to stabilize the car, there was a round concrete block in the back. The Trabant from East Germany was in high demand because it could go anywhere easily. I wasn’t able to go to university because I wasn’t accepted. In my opinion, it was because I didn’t come from a working-class background. I became a mechanic. School was free, but often young people couldn’t choose. The authorities probably had a say in the choices. I had three children and we had to live in a 61m² apartment, which isn’t much, but it was really cheap.

Food was cheap, as were books. But in many stores, you often had to wait in line. Food and other products were often in short supply, and you would often hear people say, “We’re out of that.” Having a party card opened doors. Most people had a party card, but in my opinion, they didn’t believe in it. Otherwise, it was easy to feed and clothe yourself, even if the choice was limited. When a foreigner from the West came with their car, everyone looked at the car and took pictures. Many people thought that life in the West must be paradise. What I liked about the old regime was that if you were sick, after a check-up, they left you alone, not like now. If you were sick, you were treated for free. School was free. You had more friends because people were more supportive. There was censorship, yes, but if you didn’t rock the boat and you had your party card, you could live in peace. Nowadays, it’s a more savage capitalist system, a colder system: you work, you eat; if you don’t have a job, you die. For me, life was better before, it was safer, even if you had to be careful with your spending. Although today, both husband and wife have to work to make ends meet and not have to be too careful with their spending.

3. Hungary, Szászvár, Witness 3, female, 76 years old

I worked as a nursery school teacher. The school has always had to be kept clean, and every year we repaired what needed repairing and repainted what needed repainting. Life wasn’t so bad when I compare it to life in neighbouring countries like Romania or Czechoslovakia (now two countries). Censorship was real. The state was responsible for the curriculum, and every year the students received their textbooks for free. But the authors were chosen; they were Hungarian authors accepted by the state or and also Russian authors. At the time, there weren’t many advertising posters. Travelling by bus, tram, or train was cheap, unlike today. The extended family, including grandparents, aunts, and uncles, saw each other often. Family and social life was richer than it is now. There was never a shortage of food, either because of family solidarity or because in the countryside everyone raised pigs, chickens, vegetables, etc. If money allowed people to buy or sell, it was not uncommon for people to barter.

In terms of education, everything went fairly well except for many Roma whose parents were illiterate and whose children did not attend school regularly. The authorities intervened promptly, but Roma children generally had many learning difficulties and many of them ended up in special schools for children with learning disabilities. In terms of work, there was work for everyone in the coal mine, even for the underqualified. Roma were often underqualified, but they were put to work, even if it meant sweeping the floors with five or six people when two would have been enough.

Censorship? It was more prevalent in cities than in rural areas, although you still had to be careful. Russian was a compulsory language in schools, but Hungarians did not like the Russian language very much and sometimes the teacher was understanding. Being rich? That was impossible. You could have a house or an apartment. The wealthiest also had a second home, but often it was just a small house of 25 to 40 square metres.

Of course, I know that the apparatchiks lived in greater luxury, but it was taboo to talk about it. Religious censorship was more prevalent in the cities than in the countryside, I think. Here in the countryside, I was always able to go to church without any problems, but I also had my party card. I think the authorities were more tolerant than under Rákosi... a nasty piece of work ! A Jew who didn't like Jews... Can you understand that ? Kádár showed more flexibility ; he worked for the good of the people. In fact, Romanians and others envied our living conditions.

4. Szászvár, Witness 4, male, 78 years old

I worked in the mines, but they closed in the 1980s. Why? I don't know, because I know there's still a lot of coal there. In the 1980s, we could feel that the tide was turning, that the regime was running out of steam. Prices were starting to rise, but people were still surprised by what happened in 1989.

I think life was easier and more peaceful before. We had to work, everything was very controlled. When the work was done, you had to pretend to work and everything was fine. Now it's not like that, it's not as good and you have to produce, produce, produce. I wouldn't want to be 30 now.

My miner's pension doesn't allow me to make ends meet, so I bought a small plot of land where I grow potatoes and vegetables. I used to live in an apartment, but I sold it to buy a small house with a garden to get by... as long as I'm healthy! I know that in some places there was pressure from the authorities regarding religion, but not in Szászvár. It must be said that in the Baranya region, there are many people of Germany who are very attached to the Evangelical Church. What I regret is the gradual loss of village traditions and folklore.

People used to talk to each other more. Now, there are neighbours who don't even know each other. Even in greater poverty, solidarity used to enable people to get by. Not now, if you're poor.

5. Hungary, Komlo, Witness 5, female, 77

(In Hungary, primary school lasts eight years and high school ("Gimnázium" in Hungarian) lasts four years)

I am from Komlo, a town that was thriving at the time, built from scratch to be an industrial town with coal mines.

We are Gypsies, but proud of it. We had five children. Unfortunately, we couldn't help them because we are illiterate. It must be said that our children were quite discriminated against at school, like other Gypsy children. Yet there are many Gypsy families in Komlo. Three of our children went to a school for children with learning difficulties. The other two managed to finish eighth grade but had to go to vocational school. One of them became a bricklayer and the other has no qualifications. But I don't think things are better today, even though the government is making an effort and we are represented. Life used to be better because we had worked. My husband died five years ago. He was a miner and learned the trade on the job. He worked in coal mining, but he contracted a miner's disease and had trouble breathing. He was retired at 50. He was a good viola player and played in a small orchestra of four or five musicians who performed in restaurants. He earned quite a lot of money. Now all that's over and it's only in Budapest or a few other big cities that highly skilled Gypsies still play in a few places, mainly for tourists.

We lived well in Komlo, we didn't skimp on heating, electricity or water. Now ? It's a massacre for the wallet. The food was good, cheap, and we could dress properly. We never left Hungary, not even for tourism... What for ? So people could look at us funny ? I know that because one of my cousins' lives in Vienna, Austria... And then life became very expensive. Yes, I liked it better before. There was a lot of censorship after the Second World War. We were settled down and assimilated by force. Today's Gypsies no longer live like our grandparents or great-grandparents, who could still live in caravans. The communist regime abolished all that, probably because it considered our way of life medieval. Culture ? Gypsy culture has lost much of its value and traditions, and the language is gradually being lost among young people. As for religion, we were never said anything. But be careful, under the Rákosi regime, Gypsies and Jews trembled with fear of being imprisoned or arrested... The secret police (AVH) were not tender, according to what our parents said. Life today has become less humane, I think.

6. Komlo, Witness 6, male, 76 years old

"Regime change" in 1989. Daily life was pretty much the same: go to work very early in the morning, work, come home quite late, eat, and go to sleep. Only on Sundays could people really relax and socialize and think about something other than work. But apart from that, almost everything was free: school for the children, healthcare, even if you had to pay a small amount for the doctor, rent was cheap, food was cheap... And as long as you kept quiet and the police didn't come, you could sleep peacefully. You could even drink a little during work from time to time, and the boss would offer us a drink. I worked as a farm labourer all my life. When I was younger, I thought my pension would be enough, but with the "renszerváltás" in 1989, savage capitalism came and turned everything upside down. And it's certainly no better for people of my generation. Except for the powerful, who knew how to divide the pie among themselves, but not the little people.

It's crazy to think that it was the socialist communists who seemed to be the most fervent supporters of the regime who turned their coats and started praising capitalism. Many of them lined their pockets between 1989

and 1992. High-ranking military officers were granted pensions that were astronomical (four to six times higher) than those of the rest of the population. Former politicians from the old regime switched to liberal politics on the left or right. There are even "bricks" and AVH agents who have risen to important positions. For example, Prime Minister Horn Gyula, who was an AVH agent, i.e., a member of the secret police who could interrogate or torture people. I prefer life now, even if it is unfair and difficult. Yes, there was censorship, even under Kádár, who kept a discreet watch... Everyone was watched and it was essential not to demonstrate against the regime! But is it better now, with prices skyrocketing? A Europe that increasingly resembles a socialist-communist regime? What will become of us tomorrow? I fear for my children and grandchildren.

7. Slovakia, Kosice, Witness 7, female, 75

Life was hard before, but we were used to it. There were small village festivals, folk festivals, tea dances, etc. The theatre was inexpensive, as was transportation. Energy was cheap too. But we had to live in a cramped house for a family of five. Human relationships were more direct and people were willing to help each other, unlike now... it's more of a selfish world.

Before, the Hungarian minority did not suffer any discrimination. Nowadays, there are places in the country where discrimination exists, not only against Gypsies, but also against Hungarians. People didn't seem to be in a hurry or stressed, whereas now I see the opposite. We certainly lived poorly, but differently, and we could get by, whereas now it's difficult to make ends meet! Culture and folklore, dancing and singing were part of everyday life, whereas now all that seems to have disappeared, or at least diminished.

Now, if I didn't have my little apartment, I wouldn't be able to live on the pension I receive.

For me, it was better before. As far as censorship was concerned, anyone who didn't oppose the regime or get involved in politics and led a normal, peaceful life was left alone. In the past, young people without qualifications could find work; now it's very difficult.

8. Kosice, Witness 8, male, 74

I worked as an arc welder in a factory. I learned on the job because I was given the opportunity to do so. Nowadays, I don't think I would have had that chance. Now you have to work hard to have any hope of finding a job. Worse than that, nowadays there are university graduates doing the work of ordinary office workers who, in my day, would have finished high school or not even that.

Life today is stressful and fast paced. I see this with my two children who have completed their university studies. They are always under pressure and stressed. Everyday life? We lived more simply, of course, but life was cheaper and we could afford to go out to a restaurant on the weekend and enjoy live music. Now, restaurants are a luxury, even without live music. Going to concerts was normal. Going to the theatre was also inexpensive. Nowadays, the prices are too high for me. I remember that back then, even grandparents went to the theatre, to concerts, and to restaurants. I really thought that 1989 would be a lucky year, but I've been singing a different tune for the past ten years. With the war in Ukraine on top of everything else, prices are rising... It's no longer sustainable. We're not even asked for our opinion on this war that we're ultimately financing. In a war, it's always the same: the decision-makers risk much less than the people who serve as "cannon fodder"!

Especially money to neo-Nazis, that's the last straw! For me, it was better before, even if it was a fairly authoritarian communist regime.

9. Serbia, Subotica, Witness 9, female, 76

In Tito's Yugoslavia, there wasn't the mess there is now. People didn't hate each other. I think NATO is the troublemaker. They bombed my country. Serbs will never forget that. On top of that, life is becoming too expensive. It's getting harder and harder for my children to get by. I help them as much as I can, but it's difficult. My husband died three years ago. I still grow my own vegetables because fruit and vegetables are expensive.

Life in Yugoslavia? We had everything! Mountains, the sea, a good climate, and people didn't fight each other under Tito.

It took those idiots from France, England, and America to come and destroy it. Is it better now? No! Everything is expensive, including meat. Travel is expensive, and when we go to the new country next door, we've become foreigners.

Under Tito, there was undoubtedly censorship, but we could still express ourselves... Now, I don't know... I wouldn't dare say what I think about a lot of things, because I'd probably get into trouble with some shitty association or other. The Hungarian minority? There have been clashes and ups and downs! Now things have calmed down with the current government.

Living conditions were better than they are now, in my opinion. I hope Serbia doesn't make the mistake of losing its sovereignty by becoming a member of a union of corrupt dictators.

The Westerners tore my country apart, but God will punish them! That's all I have to say.

10. Subotica, Witness 10, male, 78

My wife is ill, she has Alzheimer's, and her care is expensive. I have two children, each with two children, a girl and a boy. It's difficult for them. Everyday life was easier before than it is now. We were lucky not to be under the thumb of the USSR, with whom we nevertheless had good relations. We lived better than the Romanians, for example. The Hungarians had roughly the same standard of living as us in the 1970s. I know because I have a family on both sides.

Food was cheap, as was clothing. School was free for children. Healthcare was good enough and inexpensive. Now it's different. Yes, I regret that period of my life. People were calmer and there were fewer conflicts. The war in the 1990s ravaged the country, which was divided. Was that a good solution? No! Look at it now! There's Serbia, then the Serbs in Bosnia, Kosovo... I'm afraid the West did a lot of damage by intervening.

I used to like going to the movies and concerts, but now I'm old and can't afford it! Culturally, too, a lot has changed... Young people only listen to English songs and traditions are being lost.

11. Romania, Satu Mare, Witness 11, female, 77

I was a housewife and spent a lot of time gardening, keeping our expenses down. Ceaușescu's Romania and his Securitate henchmen ? It was shit !

Life was hard. We lived off our small plot of land, our chickens, and our pigs. It's true that water was cheap, as was wine, but we also had vineyards. Being Hungarian, I couldn't speak Hungarian to the shopkeepers. They were forbidden to speak their mother tongue. Ceaușescu did everything he could to dilute the concentration of Hungarians in towns and villages... What a piece of shit ! Before, there were about 2.5 million of us... Now there are about 1.5 million. Currently, there are ups and downs, but the nationalists hate us. Some tell us outright, "This is our land ! Go back to Hungary !"

In the 1970s ? It was better than in the 1960s or 1980s. However, life was cheaper in Hungary and there were more products to buy. We used to go there to shop because here it was really a dictatorship with the cult of personality surrounding Ceaușescu. School was free, yes, but there weren't schools everywhere.

I wouldn't want to go back to the past, even though life is difficult here. We joined Europe, but what for ? We don't have any more food on our plates. Europe is an opportunity for the rich and influential, but not for the people.

Censorship ? It was practiced daily. Everyone was afraid of everyone else because the Securitate had ears everywhere. Opponents ? They were made to disappear without any problem.

We have two children and three grandchildren ; they plan to leave the country. They see no future here and wages are very low ! Why are there such differences in wages in Europe ? Are we second-class Europeans ? Culture and folklore were quite lively in the 1970s, but not anymore, which is a shame. We will die here because we are too old to leave.

12.

Satumare, Witness 12, male, 74

I worked as a warehouse worker, then in a wood-cutting factory.

Life was hard and there was a shortage of everything, even if you had money to buy things. We had to go to Debrecen in Hungary because there were more things to buy there. Life was harder here.

Censorship affected religion and political opinions. We had to be discreet because the secret police (Securitate) were everywhere. The apparatchiks of the dictator Ceaușescu lived well, but not the population, who were dying from overwork and lack of basic necessities. We had to queue to buy things and the shop shelves were often empty. I don't regret that the regime collapsed along with its dictator. What's a shame is that the former apparatchiks were able to change sides and position themselves politically after 1989! But as my father used to say, rotting manure makes good carrots grow. But while that may be true in nature, I'm not so sure it applies to humans.

The situation for young people is often hopeless, and the only solution is to hope to find something better elsewhere. But I don't know if that's a good solution. In any case, Europe has invested in our country, sucking out our wealth, but what do people get in return? I don't see anything coming, anyway.

VI. Analysis of responses (translation)

The answers to the questions are mixed, but a majority seem to say that, although conditions were difficult, the quality of life was better in the past.

In Romania, on the other hand, there is no nostalgia, unlike among people living in Serbia.

In Hungary, although opinions are mixed, those questioned say that there were positive aspects to living conditions in the 1970s.

Romania? There is a deep resentment towards the Ceaușescu regime; living conditions seemed miserable.

In Hungary, however, this resentment does not seem to have existed, except for the generation of parents who lived through the dark days of the Rákosi regime. Kádár is seen as the man who reached a compromise with the USSR to offer Hungarians a certain standard of living.

As for present-day Slovakia, although the responses are mixed, people feel that life today is very difficult compared to 1970.

Several people questioned denounce the fact that their daily lives are not necessarily better since joining the EU. Finally, Serbs denounce the illegal bombing of their country by NATO forces, which they believe has created chaos. Censorship was discreet in Hungary and apparently virulent in Romania.

In Slovakia and Yugoslavia, censorship existed but was not as strong as in Romania.

Some respondents said that discrimination against minorities was rare in the 1970s, particularly in Yugoslavia and Slovakia. However, the Roma appear to have been discriminated against, especially in Romania and Slovakia.

The Russian-Ukrainian war seems to be a concern for those interviewed, with some very strong criticism of Western intervention in the conflict and the corruption prevailing in Ukraine. To gain a more personal insight into the testimonies, I will leave readers time to read the interviews and discover the meaning behind the words of those interviewed.

Recommended reading

1. Hélène Carrère d'Encausse, "Was Khrushchev really necessary?", *Revue française de science politique*, no. 6, 1965, pp. 1073-1074 (read online [archive])
2. Sebök, Ferenc, 2024, *Les difficultés d'apprentissage du français chez les enfants roms*, éd. EUE, ISBN : 978 6206717782
3. Sebök, Ferenc, 2024, *Les familles Roms et les difficultés d'apprentissage des enfants – Bilinguisme, conscience phonologique, difficultés langagières et d'apprentissage, traditions, culture, discriminations*, éd. EUE, ISBN : 978 6206727385
4. Sebök, Ferenc, 2024, *Discrimination and family values concerning Roma people*, Lap, Lambert Academic Publishing. ISBN : 978 6207844036
5. Sebök, Ferenc, *Roma People and their difficulties in daily life - Analysis of the answers to a questionnaire. Concerns, attitudes and behaviours*
6. *Observed in the target families: importance of customs and traditions. Reflections on the daily life of Romani people – IJAMSR Journal*, ISSN:2581-4281, Vol7, Issue 12, 2024.
7. <https://doi.org/1031426/ijamsr.2024.12.7951>
8. Stefan Auer, "Hannah Arendt, Totalitarianism and the Revolutions in Central Europe: 1956, 1968, 1989," *Eurozine*, October 25, 2006 (read online [archive], accessed October 27, 2006).
9. Victor Sebestyen, *Ungernrevolten 1956: Tolv dagar som skakade världen*, 2006, p. 286 (Swedish edition of *Twelve Days: The Story of the 1956 Hungarian Revolution*) (ISBN 91-518-4612-8). (Cites Borhi, *Hungary in the Cold War*, 2004, pp. 243–249.)
10. <https://www.kommunizmuskutato.hu/eletrajzok/rakosi-matyas>
11. <https://www.santegidio.org/pageID/30468/langID/fr/itemID/44041/La-guerre-silencieuse-du-Donbass.html>
12. <https://www.amnesty.fr/conflits-armes-et-populations/actualites/ukraine-guerre-russe-deux-ans-dix-ans-2014-2022>
13. <https://www.amnesty.fr/conflits-armes-et-populations/actualites/ukraine-guerre-russe-deux-ans-dix-ans-2014-2022>
14. <https://www.kommunizmuskutato.hu/eletrajzok/kadar-janos>
15. <https://enseignants.lumni.fr/fiche-media/00000000179/l-insurrection-de-budapest.html>
16. https://www.reflexions.uliege.be/cms/c_340113/fr/u-r-s-s-union-des-republiques-socialistes-sovietiques
17. <https://perspective.usherbrooke.ca/bilan/servlet/BMDictionnaire/1547>
18. <https://www.revueconflits.com/donbass-des-populations-divisees/>